

AN EVALUATION OF THE RULES RELATING TO DOCUMENTATION OF PARTNERSHIP CONTRACTS UNDER ISLAMIC LAW

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Abstract: *This paper evaluates the rules relating to documentation of partnership contracts in Islamic law. Partnership contracts under Islamic law cover, strictly speaking, sharikah and mudharabah. In Islamic law, there are a number of rules which guides the documentation of partnership agreements. These rules must comply, strictly, with the dictates of shari'ah for such agreement to be valid and enforceable. The major objective of this paper is to examine the rules governing the practice of documentation of partnership contracts under Islamic law. It is to find out how partnership contracts are documented and accepted under Islamic Law. The paper adopts doctrinal research methodology in gathering the relevant information in the conduct of this research. Thus, primary and secondary sources housed in both academic and public libraries are consulted. Online sources were consulted via the use of different search engines to access same such as Google Scholar, Find the Law, Elsevier, Nexus-Lexis among others. The paper observes that most partnership contracts documentation are carbon copy of the agreement under the Received English Law or Common law of England which are mostly not in compliance with shari'ah rules. Total disregard for dealing in usury, improper formula for sharing of profit and loss, dealings in uncertainties, maysir and two contracts in one contract are not shariah compliant. The paper recommends that partners should adhere to the rules of Islamic law in documentation of partnership contracts strictly instead of English or common law rules. Usurious, uncertain, game of chance, two contracts in one should be avoided.*

1.1. Introduction

The main aim of this paper is to evaluate the rules relating to documentation of partnership

contracts under Islamic law. Partnership contracts under Islamic law cover, strictly speaking, *sharikah* and *mudharabah*. In Islamic

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law, there are a number of rules which guides the documentation of partnership agreements. These rules must comply, strictly, with the dictates of *shari'ah* for such agreement to be valid and enforceable. The paper is divided into five parts. Part one is an introduction which gives an insight of the contents of the paper. Part two discusses the meaning and types of *sharikah* under Islamic Law. Part three discusses the basic rules, conditions for *sharikah* and *mudharabah* contracts as well as the types of *mudharabah*, which is also known as Islamic Banking System in modern Arabic language. Part four evaluates the documentation of partnership (*Sharikah*) and *Mudharabah* contracts or agreements under Islamic Law and rules relating to same. It further examines the samples of *Sharikah* and *Mudharabah* contracts. Part five concludes the paper which comprises the observations, recommendations and concluding remarks.

1.2. Meaning of Partnership (*Sharikah*)

Partnership, (*sharikah*) is an Arabic word, which, lexically, means sharing/merging. Technically, it means a contract signifying the conjunction of two or more persons to carry on a business to share the profits by joint investment as prevalent at the legislative period. It may be a partnership in amount of capital, labour or contribution of labour and skill, credit¹ as will be

discussed in details in due course. It is also defined as an agreement between two or more people who are qualified in law to contribute capital which is known (*maalumun*) with understanding that they will do or participate in business together with a view to making profits which shall be shared among them based on their agreement or contribution in the same manner they do when it comes to loss (*khassarah*) sharing.² It is defined as a co-mingling of two or more persons either their capital or works or obligations to earn a profit or a yield or appreciation in value and to share the loss, if any, according to their proportionate ownership.³

The types of *sharikah* include *sharikat al-milk*, *sharikat al-aqd*, *sharikat al-amwal*, *sharikatul wujuh*, *sharikatul aamal*. Except *sharikat al-milk*, all others are categories of *sharikatul aqd*.⁴ Partnership contracts refer to contracts of *shirkah* and *mudharabah* both of which in fact constitute equity participation.⁵

1.2.1. Types of Partnership (*sharikah*):

Partnership for the purpose of this paper is divided into two. Namely: *sharikah* and *mudharabah*.

Sharikah is defined as a co-mingling of two or more persons either their capital or works or obligations to earn a profit or a yield or appreciation in value and to share the loss, if any, according to their proportionate ownership.⁶

¹ Mugahal, M.A. *Islamic Concept of Partnership*, available at www.papers.ssrn.com, visited on the 06/11/19 at 11:50pm 1..

² Abubakar Jabir Al-jazairiy., *Minhaju Al-muslim* (Dar Al-fikr, 1999) 294.

³ Saqib, N.U.H. *Partnership in Shari'ah Perspective*, available at www.slideshare.net, visited on 06/11/19 at 12:00pm .3.

⁴ Ibid 4..

⁵ Hassan, R *Legal Documentations for Islamic Financing* available at www.business.com/articles visited on 16/09/19, 34.

⁶ ibid, .6.

1.2.2. Sharikatul Mulk (Partnership by Joint Ownership): This type of partnership is not for sharing of profit basically. The distribution of the proceeds or revenue under this heading is always subject to ratio of shares. Co-owners are not agents of each other but can guarantee the shares of another co-owner

1.2.3. Sharikatul Aqd (Partnership by Contract): The partners under this contract are agent of each other. Partner cannot sell his shares without other party's consent. One partner, likewise, cannot guarantee the share of other partner unlike under *sharikat* al-milk. The basic element of this partnership contract is offer and acceptance and the basic purpose of it is seeking of profit. The profit-sharing ratio is generally subject to agreement between partners. This type of *sharikah* includes *sharikatul amwal*, partnership in capital which is a contract where all the partners invest some capital into a commercial enterprise. It also includes partnership in services (*sharikatul a amal*) where all the partners jointly undertake to render some services to their customers and share the fee charges by them according to agreed ratio. Thus, a partnership by legal practitioners, medical doctors, accountants, engineers among others come within this form of partnership. Another form of *sharikatul aqd* is partnership in goodwill or credibility (*sharikatul wujuuh*) which is a partnership where all the partners will avail credit from market using their credibility

and sell the commodity to share the profit so earned at an agreed ratio.

1.3. Basic Rules and Conditions for Sharikah and Muhdarabah

This heading will mainly be devoted to examination of basic rules and conditions necessary for the formation of *sharikah* and *mudharabah* contracts or agreements. Basic principles underlying the two concepts will be highlighted first to be followed by examining the conditions of each one of them.

1.3.1. Rules and Conditions for Sharikah:

These encompass rules relating to capital which are of different forms such as liquid, in kind, to be quantified and specified, valuation of running business, cash receivables (face value and conversion rate of the day of transaction in case of currencies. There are also rules relating to capital which include merging of capital, actual merger and constructive merger. The rules relating to the management of the business include the right of each partner to take part in *musharakah* management, partners may appoint a managing partner by mutual consent or one or more of the partners may decide not to work for the *musharakah* and work as a sleeping partner instead. There are also rules relating to profit sharing. In the first place, the manner as to how profit is to be shared must be stated at the beginning of partnership. The profit should also be allocated in percentages and not in sum of money or a percentage of the capital. It is also not necessary for the shares of profit to be in

proportion to the percentage of the contributed capital. It is a rule also that a sleeping partner cannot share the profit more than the percentage of his capital. Partners may at the later stage agree to amend the percentages of profit, and on the date of distribution a partner may surrender a part of his profit to another partner. Profit formula can either be fixed or variable. The profit can also be capped to a certain amount of money. The final allocation of profit is not allowed to be based on expected profit. However, it is permissible to distribute a provisional profit, which is subject to final settlement after actual or constructive liquidation. It is also permissible for partners to decide not to distribute a portion of profit. There are, similarly, rules relating to the loss in the partnership contracts. Thus, in case the business incurs a loss, all partners will have to share the loss in exact proportion to their investment.

In partnership contracts, each partner is entitled to terminate the partnership with prior notice. The continuity of business after the withdrawal by one of the partners is allowed unlike that of the English or common law principles. The clause within which the partnership is determined is allowed. This is the same when the purpose for which the partnership is formed has been achieved or that one of the partners died or is insolvent. It should be noted that a partner is not allowed to demand the other partner to provide security in any form because their rights

and obligations are the same and they are agents for each other. However, in case of *musharakah* agreement between bank and the client, the bank shall obtain adequate security from the partner against his misconduct and negligence, if any.

1.3.2. Conditions for Valid *Sharikah*:

Under this heading, conditions for the formation of *sharikah* will be examined. For a *sharikah* to be valid (*sahihah*) under Islamic law, it must fulfill some conditions. These conditions are as follows:

1. The partners must all be muslims. This is because a non-muslim can engage in prohibited transactions which he may not know or believe in, such as transactions involving usuries. Non-muslim may also put illegal wealth (*malul haram*) in the business knowingly or unknowingly. But if these among other things are not feared from the non-muslim or that it is the *muslim* who is in total control of buying and selling or conduct of the business of the partnership, then a non-muslim can be a partner therein.⁷

2. The capital of the business (*raasul mal*) must be known (*ma'ulumun*). That is to say, the contribution of each partner is known due to the fact that the profit and loss are determined by the knowledge of the capital of the *sharikah* business. Thus, if the capital of the business or contribution of the partners is not known it may lead to consumption of other people's wealth without just course which is prohibited under the

⁷ Al-jazairiy, (n 2) .295.

law. The Glorious Qur'an prohibits this where Allah says⁸: 'O you who believe. Do not devote your property among yourselves falsely, except that it be trading by your mutual consent'

3. The profit must be shared across the products of the business. Thus, if it is stipulated by the partners that the profits made from the sale of a commodity let's say sheep or goats is for one or more of the partners and profits made from the sale of clothes is for the other partners it is not allowed but prohibited. The reason being that there are uncertainties in that (*gharar*) which is *haram*.⁹

4. The contribution of every partner must be money (*nuqud*). Thus, if a partner is to make his contribution to the business in kind (*ardun*) it must be converted to money based on the current price (*si'iri yaumih*) of the commodity he presented. This is due to the fact that *urudah* is (*gairi qimiy*) and not known at the time. Transactions with unknown commodities are prohibited under the *shari'ah*. This is *haram* and may lead to spoiling people's wealth and consuming same without just course.¹⁰

5. The business to be carried out by the partners must be legal in the eyes of the law. Thus, dealings in prohibited items such as alcoholic drinks, pigs, donkeys for the purpose of

consumption, gambling of whatever form, dealing in usury are not allowed.¹¹

1.3.3. **Mudharabah:**

Mudharabah or *Qiradh* is a partnership contract where one or more persons give out or provide their known wealth or capital (*mal*) to one or more persons to do business with understanding that the profits realized from the business is shared between them in accordance with their agreement to that effect and the loss (*khasarah*) is hinged on the capital provided alone. This is because the *amil* is not liable for loss in that what he suffered in managing the business sufficed and that he cannot be forced to shoulder another loss again.¹² It is also defined as a partnership agreement in which one party invests while the other manages the business.¹³ The one who provides capital is called '*rabbul mal*' or '*qaridh*' while the recipient of the capital or funds who provides the know-how towards carrying out the venture is called '*mudarib*' or '*muqaridh*'.¹⁴

1.3.4. Types of Mudharabah: *Mudharabah* is divided into two types. Restricted *mudharabah* (*mudharabah al-muqayyadah*) and unrestricted *mudharabah* (*mudharabah al-mudlaqah*).¹⁵ Thus, the concept of present days banking system which complies with the principles of shariah are established under *mudharabah*. Like the *shariakh*, it has certain rules relating to the

⁸ Q 4: 29.

⁹ *ibid*.

¹⁰ *ibid*.

¹¹ *ibid*.

¹² *ibid*.

¹³ Saqib, N.U.H. *Partnership in Shari'ah Perspective*, available at www.slideshare.net, visited on 17/10/19 at 4:23 pm p.21.

¹⁴ *ibid*.

¹⁵ *ibid*.

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sharing of profit realized as well as the loss incurred. It is necessary for the validity of *mudarabah* that the parties agree, right at the beginning, on a definite proportion of the actual profit to which each of them is entitled and not speculative or unrealistic profit.¹⁶ They can share the profit at any ratio they agree upon. However, in case the parties have entered into *mudarabah* without mentioning the exact proportions of the profit, it will be presumed that they will share the profit in equal ratios. Some incentives may also be given to the *mudarib* as bonus.¹⁷ Apart from the agreed proportion of the profit, the *mudarib* cannot claim any periodical salary or a fee or remuneration for the work done by him for the *mudarabah* business.¹⁸ The *mudarib* and *rabbul mal* cannot allocate a lump sum amount of profit for any party nor can they determine the share of any party at specific rate tied up with the capital provided or invested by the *rabbul mal*.¹⁹

At this point, it is imperative to contrast *mudarabah* and *sharikah*. In *musharakah*, the investment comes from all the parties while in *mudarabah* the investment is a sole responsibility of the *rabbul mal* with exclusion of the *amil*. In *musharakah*, all partners participate in the management of the business while in *mudarabah* *rabbul mal* has no right to participate in the management of the business.

Under *musharakah*, the liability is not limited but under *mudarabah* only the *rabbul mal* incurs financial liability. That is loss and the *mudarib* loses his efforts and labour. However, *rabbul mal* is only liable to the extent of his investment. In *musharakah*, all the parties can benefit from profit gained through appreciation in value of investment while in *mudarabah*, gain in appreciating investment goes to the *rabbul mal* excluding the *mudharib*.²⁰

Mudharabah is valid from the consensus of the companions of the noble prophet peace be upon him and those who followed them. It was practiced during the lifetime of the prophet peace be upon him which he approved.²¹ It was reported by Imam *Malik* in *Muwatta* that *Abdullahi ibn Umar* and *Ubaidullah Ibn Umar* met *Abu Musa Al-Ash'ariy* may Allah pleased with them all on the way at *Basra* and gave two of them an amount of money for them to hand over same to *Umar*, the caliph at the time. He guided them that they may invest the money by purchasing some goods and then subsequently sale same so that they can use the profit and give the capital to the Caliph. They did that and made profit out of the capital. But *Umar* did not give them the profit but when they confronted him with legal reasoning, he gave them half of the profit.²²

¹⁶ *Ibid*, p.32.

¹⁷ *Ibid*.

¹⁸ *Ibid*.

¹⁹ *Ibid*.

²⁰ *Ibid*.

²¹ *Jaza'iriy*, (n 2) .296.

²² *Ibid*.

1.3.5 Conditions for Valid *Mudharabah*:

1. It must be between Muslims alone who are capable of transacting business under the law. It may however be between a Muslim and non-Muslim if the investment is by the non-Muslim (*rabbul mal*) and the management is for the Muslim (*mudharib*) for there is no fear that the Muslim may engage in illegal transactions or introduces usury in the business.²³

2. The capital or investment of the *rabbul mal* must be known (*ma'alam*).

3. The ratio of profit allocated to both parties must be stated or known.

4. If there is a dispute as to the agreed proportion of profit, then the submission of the *rabbul mal* must be taken into consideration after he subscribed to an oath in addition to the said submission.

5. The *mudharib* is not permitted to take another investment from another *rabbul mal* unless approved by the first *rabbul mal*. This may lead to uncertainties/controversies.

1.4. Documentation of Partnership Contracts Under Islamic Law:

Documentation of contracts or any agreement reached under Islamic law is not a new trend. The treaties entered into between Muslims and non-Muslims during the lifetime of the prophet peace be upon him were reduced into writing.

But this does not mean that an agreement cannot be entered between the Muslims inter se or between Muslims and non-Muslims as the case may be orally. What is important is for each part to respect the terms of the agreement. It is very important to document contractual agreements under Islamic law particularly at this period of ours where deceptions and uncertainties are the order of the day. In today's economic and financial worlds, the need for documentation cannot be overemphasized. Legal documentation has become a necessary ingredient in fostering business relations and undertakings. Business whether in the so-called conventional or Islamic sense must, these days, be supported and backed up by proper documentation to guard against uncertainties and guarantee economic prosperity. Legal documentation can be defined as a document that documented some contractual relationship or grant some right to the parties involved in.²⁴ Thus, it is important for the parties who involve in any transactions to come out with a written or legal documents to reflect the agreement between them. The parties to *mudharabah* or *sharikah* contracts are required to adopt transparency, disclosure and documentation to a greater extent than even the conventional financial institutions.²⁵

²³ Ibid 297.

²⁴ Fahmy, E.Y.E. *A Holistic View of Legal Documentation from Shari'ah Perspective* available at www.mpra.ub.uni visited on 11/11/19 at 12:09 pm.5.

²⁵ Salih Fauzan, *Mulakhasul Fiqhy*, (Dar Fikr, 2017) 135.

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It is beyond contest that the Qur'an enjoins the faithful to write down and take witnesses in all transactions that involve credit one way or the other. It is clearly mentioned in the Qur'an that: O you who believe, when ye contract of debt for a fixed term, record it in writing. Let a scribe record it in writing between you in (terms of) equity. No scribe should refuse to write as Allah hath taught him, so let him write, and let him who incurth the debt dictate, and let him observe his duty to Allah hias Lord, and diminish naught thereof...²⁶

The above verse explains that the person who makes a contract a debt on a fixed term, he or she needs to record it in writing and the writer must write with sincerity. It also mentions that the person who is in debt dictate and observe his duty to Allah.

With the above background, one can safely conclude that Islamic law places high premium on documentation of contracts and the need for it becomes germane in today's reality.

1.4.1. Rules Relating to Documentation of Partnership Contracts Under Islamic Law:

The main function of legal drafting or documentation of Islamic contracts is to make sure that there is no prohibited element or anything against Islamic law that is inserted in the contract. It is also to avoid conflicts as to the terms reached between the parties. The *shari'ah*

requires that all transactions should be devoid of unlawful advantage, usury (*ribah*) by way of excess or deferment, uncertainty, risk or speculation (*gharar*). The contracts should also be devoid of gambling (*maisir*) among other prohibited acts.²⁷ Whenever a transaction involves the exchange of two counter values, it is strongly advised that the exchange should be made forth-with in order to eliminate any possibility of prohibited elements. Thus, all these are the essential elements to be taken into consideration by all the parties involved in the contract. Through a proper legal documentation, parties involved should be able to establish their rights and liabilities as well as to render them enforceable by the court of law. This is very essential in *sharikah* contract. Thus, if mallam Dauda and Malam Abu contributed N 2, 000,000 each in a partnership for thye business of buying and selling cars from abroad based on agreed loss and profit-sharing formula, such partnership agreement must, strictly, comply with the rules of Islamic law. In addition, there is need for them to document all the terms and conditions they stipulated. However, all the terms and conditions stipulated must be devoid of dealing in prohibited goods, usury, uncertainties among others. The formula for sharing of loss and profit must be stipulated in line with the rules of *shari'ah*.²⁸

²⁶ Qur'an chapter 2 v 282.

²⁷ Fahmy, (n 24) .6.

²⁸ Ibid 7.

Therefore, the knowledge in Islamic commercial law, known as *fiqhul mu'amalah*, constitutes an important branch of law dealing with issues of contracts and the legal effects arising from the contracts, be it valid, void, or voidable contract respectively. The injunctions of shari'ah are directed towards the realization of various objectives for the welfare of mankind. Legal documentation from *shari'ah* perspective must cover a variety of dealings and transactions to meet the needs of the society. The legal documentation that incorporated the rules relating to commercial transactions in accordance with the dictates of shari'ah should have certain criteria which would make it effective and serve its purposes. Thus, the rules to be taken into account to that effect are as follows:²⁹

- a. The documents must be valid according to Islamic law
- b. The documents must comply with the existing legal requirements
- c. The documents must be structured in a manner that can be enforced.³⁰

Be that as it may, the general rule relating to documentation of partnership contracts in Islamic law in particular or any other contract in general is that the document must be in line with the rules of *shari'ah* in all its ramifications. There must be prohibition of interest (*riba*), avoidance

of uncertainties (*gharar*), *qimar* and two contracts in one contract.³¹

According to *Ameerah Al-Ansariy*, the rules relating to documentation of partnership contracts under Islamic law are as follows:

- a. To ensure that the common clauses of the *mudharabah* or *sharikah* do not contravene any shari'ah principles.
- b. The elements must be free from usury, uncertainty, gambling, maisir or anything that is prohibited (*haram*) under the *shari'ah*.
- c. The common clauses in conventional legal documentation may be acceptable provided that the general rule as in (a) above is observed.³² For instance, legal representations or other representations, inclusion of warranties, affirmative and restrictive covenants are all accepted in the legal documentation of partnership as long as they are couched in such a manner that they do not contravene the shari'ah principles to that effect.³³ Issues such as stamp duty exemptions, income tax treatment such as disposal of assets, leases pursuant to *shari'ah* are accepted.
- d. In addition, partnership contract must be entered into between only parties who are all or both *muslims* except where the non-muslim is the one to provide the capital and the *muslim* to be the *mudharib* or in *musharakah* where there is no fear as to the non-muslim to perpetrate

²⁹ Ibid 9.

³⁰ ibid.11

³¹ ibid.14

³² Hassan R. *Legal Documentation for Islamic Financing* available at www.business.comma-articles, visited on 24/10/19.

³³ Ibid.

illegalities such as usury or dealing in prohibited commodities.³⁴

e. The profit sharing formula must be stated and the loss as well.

f. The contribution of each partner in *sharikah* must be known in cash not in kind unless converted to money while in case of *mudarabah* the investment of the *rabbul mal* must be ascertained.³⁵

g. Conditions and terms to be inserted must not contravene the provisions of shari'ah

h. Date of commencement of the partnership must be stated.

i. Parties must sign the agreement.

j. The nature and objectives of the business to be carried out must be specified. This includes the commodities to deal in.

k. The names and addresses of the parties and their positions relating to the contract must be stated.

1.4.2. Sample of *Sharikah* Contract Documentation Between Two Parties.

THIS MUSHARAKAH AGREEMENT is made this 12th day of Rabi'u Awwal 1441

BETWEEN:

ALHAJI GARBA MUSA of No 33, Bello Way, Sokoto in this agreement referred to as **THE FIRST PARTNER ON ONE PART**

AND:

ALHAJI UMAR BELLO of No 65, Garkuwa Road, Minanata Area, Sokoto herein referred to

as **SECOND PARTNER ON THE OTHER PART.**

The second partner, Alh Umar Bello approached the first partner Alh Garba Musa to enter into this partnership agreement to operate as dealers in buying and selling cars at No 68, As-Sudais Road, Sokoto for the period of 5 years. Thus, the *musharakah* is hereby established between the partners as follows:

The first partner provides a capital of N300, 000, 000.00 in cash for the *musharakah* business and the second partner provides N300, 000, 000.00 in cash for the business

The first and second partners shall manage the *musharakah* in the usual and customary manner and to the best interest of the partnership within the scope of a mutually agreed upon policy and strategy.

The partners to this *musharakah* contract agreed to operate an account in the name of the business with JAIZ BANK PLC both to be signatories to the account where all the money for the business shall be lodged.

The distribution of the profit shall be as follows: 40% of the profit realized from the business shall go to each partner for their investment and managerial efforts put to the business. The remaining 20% of the profit shall be used in payment of the rent of the premises, remuneration for staff of the company among other contingencies such as electricity, water and solicitors' fees among others. Any loss or losses

³⁴ Jaza'iriy, (n 2) 45.

³⁵ Ibid.

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shall solely be distributed in proportion to share in capital as in article 2 above.

All the transactions to be taken by this business must be legal in the eyes of *shari'ah* to the effect there shall be no dealings in usury, *gharar*, forbidden items and transactions. In essence, it is all the way *shari'ah* compliant.

SIGNED BY THE PARTNERS:

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

IN THE PRESENCE OF:

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

1.4.3. Sample of Mudharabah Contract Documentation

THIS MUDHARABAH AGREEMENT is made on the 28th day of Rabi' Auwal 1441 AH

BETWEEN:

IBRAHIM ABDULLAHI of No 8, Kamba Road, Sokoto hereinafter referred to as '**RABBUL MAL**' ON ONE PART

AND:

ARZIKA INUWA of No 10, Zaria Road, Sokoto hereinafter referred to as '**MUDHARIB**' ON THE OTHER PART.

The *mudharib* approached the *rabbul mal* to enter into a *mudharabah* agreement to trade in textiles through import and distribution in the location of *Khairat Plaza Sokoto* which is owned by the *mudharib* for a period of four years.

THUS, a *mudharabah* is hereby agreed between the two partners as follows:

The *rabbul mal* provides N 700, 000, 000.00 for the purpose of using it as a principal capital for the *mudharabah*.

The *rabbul mal* has the full right to inspect accounts, books, records of the *mudharabah* at any time and place.

The *rabbul mal* has full right to intervene whenever he notices serious managerial lapse occasioned by acts inimical to the *mudharabah* or against the principles of *shari'ah*

The *mudharib* shall take full charge of managing this *mudharabah* for the purpose of maximizing its profit and to liquidate all its properties by its closing date.

The *mudharib* shall discharge his assignment with full honesty and maximum loyalty to its objectives.

The *mudharib* shall maintain accurate, exclusive and comprehensive accounts of the *mudharabah*.

The *mudharib* pledges to supply the bank with quarterly report. And it is understood that he

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shall use his expertise and facilities of the business in the fulfillment of the objectives of this *mudharabah*.

The *mudharib* is not allowed to mix his own or others' funds with funds of the *mudharabah*, he should not also trade beyond Sokoto Kebbi and Zamfara states unless with the written consent of the *rabbul mal*.

The *mudharib* should not deal in usury, *uncertainties*, prohibited goods or any other prohibited items under the *shari'ah*.

All banking transactions of the *mudharabah* shall be exclusively affected in, with and through Ja'iz bank only Jaiz Bank unless otherwise with the consent of the *rabbul mal*.

The profit is defined as any amount in excess of the principal to be calculated at the end of each financial year.

The distribution of the profit shall be as follows:

- a. 40% to the *Rabbul mal*
- b. 60% to the *mudharib*
- c. Any losses shall solely be borne by *rabbul mal*.

The duration of this *mudharabah* is four years from the commencement date as indicated above and the *mudharib* is required, by the end of such period, to liquidate all assets of the *mudharabah*,

SIGNED BY THE RABBUL MAL

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

SIGNED BY THE MUDHARIB

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

BOTH IN THE PRESENCE OF:

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

NAME:

ADDRESS:

OCCUPATION:

SIGN/DATE:

1.5. Conclusion

Thus, from the above samples of partnership contract legal documentation, there is conformity with the rules of *shari'ah* relating to same except where it is agreed that the *rabbul mal* shall bear any loss arising from the contract which out rightly negates the principles of Islamic Law which dictates that loss and profit must be shared by the parties in that occasion. In these days, there are a number of partnership contract documentations which complies with the rules of drafting same under Islamic law. This brings us to the assessment of such legal documentations.

For instance, *mudharabah* partnership contracts are being documented in many quarters where the *rabbul mal* will only handover money or capital to the *mudharib* to do business without specifying which business to do or not to do whether or not it contradicts the

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rules of *shari'ah*. In this regard, the *mudharib* may transact in any item whether forbidden or uncertain or may lead to usury. What is important to the *rabbul mal* is his percentage. As long as he is getting his share of the profit as agreed, there is no problem. Any partnership contract couched or drafted in this manner violates some rules relating to documentation of partnership contracts under Islamic law. Exclusion of prohibited transactions is important in securing the validity of legal documentation from Islamic perspective. It is reasonable to state that all Islamic financial experts agree generally that any Islamic partnership contracts should exclude dealing in usury, *gharar* and *maysir*.³⁶

Likewise, the percentage of profit to be given to the *rabbul mal* must only be from actual profit not speculative as with the case of many partnerships' contracts agreement nowadays. For instance, a case was brought before Economic and Financial Crimes Commission Sokoto Zonal Office where a *rabbul mal* gave the sum of N 6000, 000.00 to *mudharib* for him to deal in importation and distribution of used cars from abroad in Sokoto State. It is not stipulated in the agreement that the *mudharib* should not engage in dealings involving usury, uncertainties or even prohibited cars such as ones without custom duties. There is no clause relating to sharing of profit or loss. The only important stipulation in the agreement favouring the

rabbul mal is that at the end of every month the *mudharib* must give N600, 000.00 to *rabbul mal* as a fixed share of the imaginary profit. There is also no stipulation as to loss in case it happens. So, the *mudharib* who is in need of capital to do business accepted. He started giving the amount as agreed at the end of every month not taking into consideration whether or not a profit is realized. With this development, the *rabbul mal* received more than the capital he gave to the *mudharib* and the *mudharib* could not understand what happened to the capital of the *rabbul mal*. The *rabbul mal* brought a complaint to recover the capital. This has, indeed, occasioned injustice on the part of the *mudharib*.

A partnership agreement between the partners to do business by acting as attorneys or legal and corporate consultants or as medical practitioners as it happens in the cases of law firms and clinics are not devoid of either clause violating rules relating to drafting of partnership contracts under Islamic law or exclusion of same. Thus, two or more legal practitioners coming together to do business as solicitors and advocates usually draft an agreement in that regard. The formula for sharing profit is always there depending on their agreement. What is usually missing is a stipulation that none of the partners should institute or defend any case either civil or criminal if, to the best knowledge of the partners, the persons or persons to be represented is khain

³⁶ Fahmy, (n 24) .65.

or criminal. Thus, any partnership agreement which agree to defend the unjust client or criminal violates the rules of *shari'ah*. This is the injunction of the Quran where Allah, the highest proclaimed that 'be not an advocate on behalf of the treacherous'³⁷ also in another verse Allah will challenge those who defended the criminals in the world on the day of judgement that if there is anyone who can defend them before Allah. A question which they cannot answer on that day. The legal and medical practitioners in their partnership agreements must specifically state the terms of the agreement to be in tandem with dictates of *shari'ah*. Mostly, they couched their agreements based on the practices of our colonial masters. They include or exclude terms which violate principles or rules of *shari'ah*.

Taking a look to the present banking system as compared to *mudharabah* agreement, the legal documentation as prepared leaves much to be desired. The bank, as *mudharib*, is not restricted from dealings in usury, uncertainty, *maysir* or entering two contracts in one contract. In essence, there are no clauses in the documentation specifying some restrictions. The sharing of profit and loss are not *shari'ah* compliant. The *mudharib* under the banking system may be a non-Muslim which cannot happen under Islamic laws without some qualifications.

The present-day motorcycle hiring which is often called insurance is to the effect that a partner will

purchase motorcycle with his capital at the rate of N 200, 000.00, for example and handover same to the *amil*. The agreement is couched in such a way that the *rabbul mal* will be receiving a fixed amount such as N 1000 or N 1500 daily depending on the agreement between them for a stated period such as 11 months or 10 months. Within this period, under any circumstances, the *amil* must give the agreed amount to the *rabbul mal*. At the end of the payment across the agreed number of months, the motorcycle now belongs to the *amil*. However, if for any reason the *amil* defaulted after paying for the period of 7 months of the 11th months for instance, the *rabbul mal* can exercise his power of seizure of the motorcycle leaving the *amil* empty. This is the most prevalent type of partnership contract in Sokoto, Kebbi, Zamfara and many other states of the Federation. There are some uncertainties associated with this partnership contract. Thus, documenting same as such violates rules of *shari'ah*; the *rabbul mal* will not suffer loss in case of any eventuality.

1.5.1. Observations:

It has been observed that majority of partnership documentations under Islamic law are characterized by the followings:

1. Carbon copy of the agreement under the Received English Law or Common law of England which are mostly not in compliance with *shari'ah* rules.
2. Total disregard for dealing in usury.

³⁷ Q Ch.4 v 105 and 109.

3. No proper formula for sharing of profit as is obtainable under Islamic law of partnership.

4. Dealings in uncertainties.

5. Dealings in *maysir*.

6. Two contracts in one contract

1.5.2. Recommendations

In view of the above observations, the following are proffered as recommendations:

1. Partners should adhere to the rules of Islamic law relating to documentation of partnership contracts rather than the rules of English law which mostly contradict those of *shari'ah*.

2. Partners or their solicitors should avoid usurious transactions in drafting partnership contracts.

3. All partnership agreements under Islamic Law should avoid uncertainties.

4. Avoiding *maysir* or *qimar* (game of chance/speculation).

5. Avoid two contracts in one contract

6. Insert proper and *shari'ah* compliant formula regarding sharing of profit and loss.

1.5.3. Concluding Remarks

Islamic law leaves no stone unturned in respect of the rules relating to legal documentation of partnership contracts. The essence of the rules is to ensure that none of the parties or partners suffers any economic hurt. They are also to ensure that the whole business is blessed in that the moment one of the partners manifests any sign of cheat or deceit (*khiyanah*) the whole business would be cursed by the Almighty Allah

and the blessings would be wiped out from same. Thus, *shari'ah* requirements must be incorporated into legal documentation of partnership contracts.

At this juncture, it is important to note that the *shari'ah* rules relating to partnership generally and documentation of its agreement in particular is aimed, as it were, at sanitising the entire economic and business terrain so that capital and labour, profit and loss will continue to be mutually complementing and guaranteeing partners in accordance with the dictates of *shari'ah*.